

Study on Work Life Balance among Rural Employees

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ABSTRACT

Work-life balance is managing activity between paid work and other activities that are important to us - including spending time with family, taking part in sport and recreation, volunteering or undertaking further study. This study is undertaken to study on Work Life Balance among the rural employees. The main objective of the study was to gain an insight into Work Life Balance among the rural Employees and to assess the time spend by the employees for work and personal work. To address the research objective indepth personal interview with well-structured questionnaire was done with 100 respondents working in Textile Industry at Theni District of Tamilnadu. Respondents were selected by simple random sampling technique.. This research provides suggestions to improve worklife balance to offer real benefits for employers and employees to build strong communities and productive businesses in rural areas of Tamilnadu.

Key Words: Work life Balance, Rural Employees, Working hours, Family, Employeee

1. INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance managing activity between paid work and other activities that are important to us - including spending time with family, taking part in sport and recreation, volunteering or undertaking further study. Work life of employees may either balances of imbalanced. In recent years there has been immense change in work life balance of employees. Balanced work life practices makes the employees to manage multiple responsibilities at home, work and in the community effectively without guilt or regret, able to work in flexible ways so that earning an income and managing family/other commitments become easier, being a part of supportive workplace that values and trusts staff, have a good quality of life, an enjoyable work life and career progression, good health and so on. Imbalance work life will provide stress, lack of self-motivation, poor health, poor quality of work, decreases productivity and so on. In the present scenario work life balance is a greater problem among the employees. All these factors make work life balance as an emerging and

relevant topic to be discussed. The study undertaken here is an attempt to study the work life balance of rural employees in Textile Industry of Tamilnadu.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Alam et al. (2009) explored the correlation between work family imbalance and working hours among three focused groups, such as, teaching professionals and two groups from corporate houses. It was found that work life imbalance was not a problem for workers working for 5-7 hours a day, on the other hand it is a crucial factor for female executive working for 9-10 hours per day. Majority of female executives and few teaching professionals accounted to have work family conflict because of 9 -10 hours work every day.

The article, *Work-life balance of shift workers* (Williams, 2008), analyzed employees according to day shift, evening shift, rotating-shift, and split or irregular shift hours. Additionally, gender and marital status were considered. The study exhibited that first-shift employees are getting highest levels of work-life satisfaction, followed by second-shift employees. Furthermore, rotating-shift workers demonstrated a 73% satisfaction rating while split and irregular shift employees exhibited a rating of 65% satisfaction. As far as the variance from male to female, women displayed greater work-life imbalance (at a rate of 27% versus 19%) although shift affiliation was a non-factor. In regard to marital status, first-shift employees whose significant others are also employed full-time exhibited 75% satisfaction and those whose spouses are employed part-time exhibited a 77% satisfaction rate.

Bardoel et al. (2008) in his study he identified gender, children, family structure, health outcome issues related to work life, government policy and legislation, organization approaches to work life and work family issues, work characteristics, industry in which the respondent are working, as the major factors that have dominated work life balance of employees in Australia and New Zealand

Sjoberg (2008) identified that emotional intelligence plays major role for the successful well balanced life. It was found that family/leisure interference with work and work interference with family/leisure have strongly negative correlation with emotional intelligence. Thus the study shows that high emotional intelligence was associated with a healthier work life balance

Kinnunen and Mauno (2007) in their study among employees of municipal and social healthcare, manufacturing for exports, a bank and a supermarket identified that interference from work to family was more frequent than interference from family to work among both sexes. On the other hand, there was no gender variation in experiencing either work to family or family to work conflict.

Study of Taiwanese managers, Hsieh et al. (2005) state that only limited number of Taiwanese manager's face difficult in balancing work and personal lives and work interfered with personal life more frequently than personal life did with the work.

Wesley and Muthuswamy (2005) under took a study among 230 teachers in an engineering college at Coimbatore, India and found that work to family conflict was more prevalent than family to work conflict, thus indicating that interference of work into family was more than interference of family into work. This study also did not find any gender differences in the experience of work to family or family to work conflict and argued that household activities are being shared by both men and women as well as financial resources also shared by both for paid homemaker.

Butler et al. (2005) in his report mentioned that 91 percent respondents employed in non-professional occupations for more than 14 days personalized conflict between work and family. Outcome of the study showed that there was considerable variation every day in work to family conflict (WFC) and work to family facilitation (WFF) that was expected from daily job characteristics.

Drew and Murtagh (2005) examined the attitude and experience of male and female senior managers towards work life balance. The study was undertaken in an Irish company which has work life balance as one of its strategic corporate objective. The study reveals that long working hours was the major obstacle to maintain work life balance. Many studies reported negative correlation between working hours and conflict between work and family.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

- To gain an insight into Work Life Balance among the rural Employees
- To assess the mental status of experienced workers

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To address the study a Descriptive research was undertaken which includes surveys and fact-finding enquires of different kinds, which help the researchers to measure the effectiveness of work life balance among the employees working in Textile industry in rural areas of Tamilnadu. Probability sampling method was used to collect primary data. The item selected from the population constitutes the sample size. 100 employees from all cadre was taken as sample respondents. Questionnaire method was used to collect primary data from the sample respondents. The questionnaire consists of various questions focusing on the objective of the study and secondary data were collected from books, journals and websites. The data thus collected were analyzed using simple percentage and chi-square analysis.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

Employees of every enterprise are the driving force for the success of that respective enterprise. It is difficult for every enterprise to maintain work life balance among its employees in today's business environment. Lack of work life balance provides negative impact on labor turnover, enterprise prospect and benefit, rapport among employees, work attitude and organizational culture. Following discussion shows the result of significant relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work, significant relationship between education qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work, significant relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

Hypothesis:1

H_0 : There is a significant relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work

H_1 : There is no significant relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work

Table 1 shows the relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work

TABLE : 1 Relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work

	Below 25years	25 – 35 years	35 – 45 Years	above 45 years	Total
Long working hours	8	11	5	1	25
Compulsory overtime	7	7	4	4	22
Shift wor	1	29	11	1	42
meetings/training after office hours	2	6	2	1	11
	18	53	22	7	100

Chi-square Test was done to measure the significant relationship between Age and respondents balance in work and family commitments on the work life balance of Employees. Table 2 shows the chi square test analysis to to measure the significant relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work

Table : 2 Chi-square Test Statistics

O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
8	4.5	3.5	12.25	2.72
11	13.25	- 2.25	5.06	0.38
5	5.5	- 0.5	0.25	0.04
1	1.75	-0.75	0.56	0.32
7	3.96	3.04	9.24	2.33
7	11.66	-4.66	21.71	1.86
4	4.84	-0.84	0.70	0.14
4	1.54	2.46	6.05	3.92
1	7.56	-6.56	43.03	5.69
29	22.26	6.74	45.42	2.04
11	9.24	1.76	3.09	0.33
1	2.94	-1.94	3.76	1.28
2	1.98	0.02	0.04	2.02
6	5.83	0.17	0.02	4.95
2	2.42	-0.42	0.17	0.07
1	0.77	0.23	0.05	0.06
				C.V 28.15

Calculated value > Tabulated value **28.15 > 16.919**

The table value of χ^2 for 9 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis - 2

H_0 :There is a significant relationship between Education Qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work

H_1 :There is no significant relationship between Education Qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work

Table 3 shows the relationship between qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work

TABLE – 3 Relationship between qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work

	Post Graduate	Under Graduate	Diploma	Higher Secondary	Total
Less than 5 days	2	5	1	1	9
5 days	9	5	2	3	19
6 days	17	23	7	15	62
7 days	0	0	7	3	10
	28	33	17	22	100

Table 4 shows chi-square analysis of significant relationship between Qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work

TABLE – 4 Chi-square Test Statistics

O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
2	2.52	-0.52	0.27	0.10
5	2.97	2.03	4.12	1.38
1	1.53	-0.53	0.28	0.18
1	1.98	-0.98	0.96	0.48
9	5.32	3.68	13.54	2.54
5	6.27	-1.27	1.61	0.25
2	3.23	-1.23	1.51	0.46
3	4.18	-1.18	1.39	0.33
17	17.36	-0.36	0.12	6.91
23	20.46	2.54	6.45	0.31
7	10.54	-3.54	12.53	1.18
15	13.64	1.36	1.84	0.13
0	2.8	-2.8	7.84	2.8
0	3.3	-3.3	10.89	3.3
7	1.7	5.3	28.09	16.52
3	2.2	0.8	0.64	0.29
				$C.V = 37.16$

Calculated value > Tabulated value

37.16 > 16.919

The table value of χ^2 for 9 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis - 3

H_0 : There is a significant relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

H_1 : There is no significant relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

Table 5 shows relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

Table – 5 Relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

	Under 5 years	5 – 10 years	10 – 15 years	15 – 20 years	Above 20 years	Total
Very unhappy	0	3	0	3	0	6
Unhappy	11	3	3	2	0	19
Indifferent	7	10	5	3	3	28
Happy	3	15	4	8	1	31
Very happy	2	5	6	3	0	16
	23	36	18	19	4	100

Table 6 shows the chi-square analysis of significant relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees

Table :6 Chi-square Test Statistics

O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
0	1.38	-1.38	1.90	1.38
3	2.16	0.84	0.70	0.32
0	1.08	-1.08	1.16	1.08
3	1.14	1.86	3.45	3.03
0	0.24	-0.24	0.05	0.24
11	4.37	6.63	43.95	10.05
3	6.84	-3.84	14.74	2.15
3	3.42	-0.42	0.17	0.05
2	3.61	-1.61	2.59	0.71
0	0.76	-0.76	0.57	0.76
7	6.44	0.56	0.31	0.04
10	10.08	-0.08	0.0064	0.00063
5	5.04	-0.04	0.0016	0.00031
3	5.32	-2.32	5.38	1.01
3	1.12	1.88	3.53	3.15
3	7.13	-4.13	17.05	2.39
15	11.16	3.84	14.74	1.32

4	5.58	-1.58	2.49	0.44
8	5.89	2.11	4.45	0.75
1	1.24	-0.24	0.05	0.04
2	3.68	-1.68	2.82	0.76
5	5.76	-0.76	0.57	0.10
6	2.88	3.12	9.73	3.38
3	3.04	-0.04	0.0016	0.00052
0	0.64	-0.64	0.40	0.64
				CV = 33.79

Calculated value > Tabulated value **37.16 > 26.296**

The table value of χ^2 for 16 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 26.296. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

6. DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to gain an insight into Work Life Balance among the rural Employees and to assess the mental status of experienced workers. The research design was developed to establish relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work, relationship between education qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work, relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees. Three hypotheses were frames after general literature review

Hypothesis 1 was to find the relationship between age of the respondents and their commitments towards work. From the analysis it was inferred that the table value of χ^2 for 9 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2 was relationship between Education Qualification and number of days in a week the respondents work. From the analysis it was found that the table value of χ^2 for 9 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 3 was relationship between the mental condition and years of experience of the employees. From the analysis the table value of χ^2 for 16 degree of freedom at 5% level of significance 26.296. The calculated value of χ^2 is much higher than table value and hence the result of experiment does not support the hypothesis, therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

7. RECOMMENDATION

- Employers have to organize wellness programs to improve the physical and mental condition of the employees to develop the work life balance of employees.
- Enough compensation has to be provided to dedicated workers in the form of fringe benefits, medical packages and retirement packages.
- Every organization in rural areas should reconsider the working hours to achieve work life balance

- Measures has to be introduce to improve the organisation culture and morale to attain favorable work life balance
- Regular yoga and meditation programs can be organized to develop the depressed status of the employee

8. CONCLUSION

A cheerful and vigorous worker will spring improved turnover, make moral choices and absolutely contribute to organizational goal. An assured good work life will not only attract young and new talents but also retain the existing experienced talents. Work life distress things such as timings of employees, his or her productivity, his or her leave facilities, etc Work life balance must be maintained effectively to ensure that all workforces are performing at their uttermost potential and free from stress and strain. So it is up to the organization to focus on their workers and improve their work life so that work life balance can be maintained

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